

The Primorial Coupling Constants Series and Particle Physics – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the second representation of the coupling constants series, i.e. spin; it is possible to construct a new and simple way that can be used for the discipline of particle physics. Such a method could simplify or add an additional liar to the Feynman diagrams. It is easier to understand as it involves only basic mathematical operations and four categories classified by spin.

Introduction

Particle physics is mainly done and analyzed by the Feynman diagrams and Feynman rules. Those are describing the process of emission and absorption of bosons by fermions. By using the recent insight of the coupling series and bosons to be net curvature isomorphic to primes or one, located on the prime critical line, new insights and predictions can be made regarding interactions.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

Shifting to spin representations:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

In addition, to our category classification based on spin:

Spin zero: ($2N$ variations)

Matter with spin one-half: ($2N$ variations + 3)

Bosons with spin one: ($2N$ variations + 3) + N_V

Bosons with higher spin integers: ($2N$ variations + 3) + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + ... →

Suppose we want to know what will happen if two particles will annihilate each other. All we have to do is pair them together and search for the kind of spin that will be the result of the two destroying one another and vice versa. That is an elegant and not before presented in any other theory to do particle physics, and how we built the electron positron pairing to yield the higgs boson particle.

$$ee^+ \rightarrow H^0 \quad (1.33)$$

$$ee^+ \rightarrow 4N$$

Equivalently how the framework also predicted photon anti-photon pair to yield a spin zero, Higgs particle.

$$\left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

$$\left[2N_2 - \frac{1}{2}\right] - \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 - 1$$

$$2N_2 - 1 + 2N_2 + 1 = 4N_2 \quad (1.34)$$

$$\gamma\gamma^- \rightarrow H^0 \quad (1.35)$$

Alternatively, the particle wave duality by an additional photon varying the total spin by half unit:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + \frac{3}{2}$$

Therefore, to understand an interaction, all you have to do is sum up the numerical values based on the coupling series in the second representation. If there is an even amount, there is certain amount of absorption or emitting. If there is an even amount of bosons including the invariant (3) the bosonic packet will behave like a wave, else it will behave as a particle. Spin is subject of change of the second representation. If we pair particles in annihilation interaction, the spin goes toward the first or second, or lower category such as the higgs field. As the author domain of expertise is mathematical physics to him those interactions in equations (1.33) and (1.35) are mere predictions.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series – Spin" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series – Electrons" In: (2021)